

SOME COMMENTS ON THE LATIN NAMING OF CHEMICAL TERMS, OXIDES AND ACIDS IN MEDICINE

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Abstract. This is the abstract of Chemical terminology, names of chemical elements acids and oxides. In this article, I have mentioned about the chemical terminologies of the elements some of the important acids and oxides. I have also mentioned about the uses of these substance in our body how they help in various metabolic activities etc.

Key words: terms, communication, foundation, inorganic, concept, globalization, multicomponent, chemical elements

Introduction

In easy words, elements are substance that cannot be broken down into other substances. The basic structure or the foundation of an element is an atom, and each element is distinguished by the number of protons, neutrons and electrons it has. Elements are also known as naturally occurring substance that is found all around the universe. It is said by scientist that most of the elements in earth are from space where it crashed in the form of an asteroid millions of years ago. Some of the well-known elements are Hydrogen, Lithium, Beryllium, Carbon, Gold, aluminium, etc.

Rapid development of all areas of science, including chemical characterized by intense professional activity specialists and the growing demands of civilization, determines the emergence a large number of terms reflecting new knowledge, which in conditions globalization requires a unified approach to their study and application. Term, appeared to denote any name must correctly be perceived and used by representatives of relevant areas all over the world, since disparate interpretation of the meanings of the same lexical units in different languages, in our case Russian and English, causes confusion resulting in distorted understanding and practical application. To avoid making mistakes in use these terms need to be systematized, regulated and

streamlined, since unsystematic nature makes it difficult, and sometimes impossible, to correctly use especially in a professional communication environment.

An acid is a molecule which has the ability to either give/ take a proton known as Bronsted Lowry acid or forming a covalent also with an electron pair known as Lewis acid. In acids there 2 categories which are organic and inorganic acids. Organic acids are organic compounds which possess acidic properties. The thing that differentiates acid and a base is acids possess Hplus ions and bases possess OH- ions. One of the most common organic acid which is present is carboxylic acid which has the molecular formula of RCOOH. Inorganic acids are acids which are derived from one or more inorganic compounds . Almost most of the inorganic acid form hydrogen ions and conjugate base ions when dissolved In water. Some of the examples of acids are which are HCL, NACL, etc... and some of the examples of inorganic acids are Nitric acid, phosphoric acid etc. and examples of organic acid are lactic acid, formic acid, tartaric acid, malic acid etc..

Oxides are naturally occurring chemical compounds with one, 2 or more oxygen atoms with another element. They are also binary compounds of oxygen with another element. There are 3 types of oxides phosphoros, sulfur and chlorine which form molecular oxides. The oxides are formed when an atom, a molecule or even an ion comes in contact with oxygen. While this happens it transfers electrons and changes to get a more stable structure in its electron valence shells. Some of the examples of oxides are Aluminium oxide, Carbon dioxide, Sulfur dioxide, calcium oxide.

Consequently, the purpose of the study is to conduct a structural-semantic, orthographic and prosodic analysis of some chemical terms in medicine to identify differences in their structure, meanings, accents, and spelling in Russian and English and taking into account these differences when transmitting the lexical units in question from Russian to English and vice versa. All these differences represent importance when translating terms from one language to another. Accounting, for example, structure of a multicomponent term, allows you to identify the main and dependent words, their relationships and interdependencies, which determines adequacy of their transmission from English into Russian and from Russian into English. Differences in the typological structure of these languages necessitates studying the composition of terms in them.

At present, the achievements of any science cannot be shared only one specific country. The value of any science is determined today at the global level. However, for effective collaboration scientists from different countries need generally accepted terminology in all its spheres, including chemical ones, since here there are also various specific terms.

One of the sections of chemistry that requires special attention is medicinal chemistry - a scientific field whose subject of study is the search and creation of medicinal substances, identifying the relationship between chemical structure and physiological activity, as well as the design of structures with a given activity.

Modern medical terminology is the result centuries-old development of world healing and medical science. Medical terminology is presented in different national languages and includes a significant proportion of lexical and word-forming units of common linguistic origin, as well as common structural models. This etymological, word-formation and structural commonality of the terms under consideration is determined by the all-encompassing stable influenced for many centuries and especially nowadays by two classical languages of the ancient world - ancient Greek and Latin. Despite the etymological, word-formation and structural common roots of medical terms, the study showed the presence of significant differences in these terms in the Russian and English languages, ignoring them can lead to a highly distorted perception of medical representatives in oral and written speech in different countries. In the scientific community, there are many approaches to interpreting the concept of "term", based mainly on two concepts.

Proponents of the first concept advocate "unambiguity, brevity, the ability of a term to express a strictly defined concept," calling terms special words. In other words, the properties of the term are minimized in their content characteristics and brought to the negative antipodes of the corresponding properties of commonly used words.

As a rule, the names of the vast majority of compounds in the layer of lexical units under consideration consist of two components. This fact is also confirmed by the results of studies of other formations special terminology. For example, "the most numerous are two-component eponyms, that is, terms consisting of an eponym and nuclear word" [6, p. 24]. Here the similarity of the recording form appears in English and Russian, but there are some differences. It is that in English terms, where the order of listing components corresponds to the order they are listed in the formula, the main

word is placed at the end. In Russian, it is customary to put the main word first place. So, for KCl in Russian the name will be “potassium chloride” and in English - "potassium chloride". The names will sound similar for NaBr (“sodium bromide” – “sodium bromide”), MgO (“magnesium oxide” – "magnesium oxide"), CaCl₂ ("calcium chloride"), Li₂CO₃ (“lithium carbonate” – “lithium carbonate”), N₂O (“dianitrogen oxide” – "dinitrogenoxide"), etc.

Conclusion

Chemical elements, acids and oxides or essential to our day to day life, also in all walks of life it can be seen everywhere. Without these nothing is achievable in the world of science. Further prospects for research work in this direction are seen in a more detailed consideration of individual thematic groups medical terminology. In modern times, it seems relevant to study various aspects of medical terminology based on means computer information technologies. As practical applications of the research results, one can consider the creation of a dictionary of chemical terms in medicine, its intended use by representatives of medicine in English-Russian speaking countries, with further inclusion in teaching aids for training specialists in the areas under consideration.

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